
ELECTRIFICATION OF RURAL AREAS USING PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS: STAND ALONE SYSTEMS

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Abstract: Potential for Limpopo is quite high in photovoltaic technology (PV), based on the fact that it is abundant in solar resources. Sizing/Design of stand-alone photovoltaic system (SAPVs) to electrify rural areas is a suitable alternative to supply power to the rural households. This paper presents a study on sizing of PV array module to supply the required electricity for the village. The electrical load and radiation data of the typical household in the target village was taken account to in sizing of the proposed stand-alone photovoltaic system. MATLAB software was carried to size PV system without battery.

Index Terms - Rural Electrification, Stand-alone Photovoltaic system.

I. INTRODUCTION

In South Africa at least 4.5 million people do not have access to electricity which means they are unable to meet their energy demands. This lack of energy disproportionately afflicts those who are living in rural areas. The prime motivation for studying off-grid electrification comes from the idea that access to electricity improves people's lives in so many ways [1]. The best economical alternative energy source is renewable energy. This is due to the fact that over the years, the sun has been producing free energy due to the solar radiation that was and is being intercepted by the earth's surface thereby generating Mega-watts of power [1]. In renewable energy (Solar PV) framework it is important to know the measure of daylight accessible at a specific area at a given time. The two basic systems that describe sun based radiation are the solar radiance (or radiation) and solar insolation. The solar radiance is the instantaneous power density in units of kw/m^2 [2]. The solar radiance shifts for the duration of the day from 0 kw/m^2

during the evening to a greatest of about 1 kw/m^2 . It is emphatically dependent on area and neighbourhood climate. The rural areas in Southern Africa experience some of the highest levels of solar radiance and solar insolation, thus these rural areas can be electrified by a lot of renewable energy sources with photovoltaic systems being regarded as some of the most user friendly ones as opposed to the others [2]. Nqadu location experiences some of the highest levels of solar radiation in the world. With an average solar radiation that varies between 4.5 kWh/m^2 compared to about 3.6 kWh/m^2 in parts of the world. The electrical load in this location is usually small hence it is only economical to use PV systems to meet their energy demands.

This study aims to provide electrification to developing rural areas thereby alleviating poverty and increasing the living standard of the poor [3]. For this propose, a modified sigmoid function was used to approximate electrical characteristics of PV panels.

METHODOLOGY

A. Modelling and Simulation of PV System

Figure 1. Block Diagram of PV Simulation Module

Fig. 1 shows the proposed PV Module where the first block, ‘Behavioural PV Model’ performs theoretical calculations based on physics of the PV cell thus yielding the nominal values of voltage and current generated by the panel. The second block drives to the electrical load according to I - V Characteristics. Depending on the load value, the voltage drop over load current and voltage current are adjusted according to the maximum power provided by PV panel [5].

II. EXPERIMENTATION

B. PV Modelling Behavioural

The physics of the PV cell is very similar to that of the classical diode with a pn junction. When the junction absorbs light, the energy of absorbed photons is transferred to the electron-proton system of the material, creating charge carriers that are separated at the junction. An ideal PV cell is assumed to have no series loss and no leakage to ground [5].

i. Electrical Circuit Model

Figure 2. Equivalent Electrical Circuit Model

Fig.2 shows the Equivalent electrical circuit model of PV cells. The losses of this model are expressed by using resistances in equivalent circuits. The behavioural model of the proposed PV Model is based on this circuit model where I_{ph} , current source is produced by the photons and is constant at a fixed value of temperature and radiation [4].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Power Used by 50 Households of Nqadu Location

	Wattage
Total Used per House in kW	0.940
50 Households	47
PV System P_{out} in kW	50

Table 1 shows the power that 50 people of Nqadu location need to meet their demands. The final power that PV Systems supplies to this village is 50 kW as the village is in need of 47 kW [5].

Figure 3 Simulink Simulation

Fig. 3 shows the Simulink simulation of a PV array supplying three phase AC Distribution System to ensure that the energy needs of the villagers of Nqadu Location are met while improving their livelihood as well. In order to reduce negative impacts of possible reverse current of DC/AC converter on PV module, a diode is used [6].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the sizing and design of a suitable PV System suitable for the electrification of Nqadu Location. Fifty households were taken so as to theoretically determine sizing of this PV Array by the usage of MATLAB and SIMULINK. The 50 kW consisting of a PV array, inverter, and controller were used. Modelling renewable energy sources for a large-scale power system integration simulation is more important today, because these simulation tools will be a part of optimal design and intelligent management process.

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